

IMPLEMENTING TASK-BASED APPROACH IN TEACHING READING COMPREHENSION

Dinara Ruslanovna Saitxanova

docent of history and philology faculty, foreign languages and literature department

University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences, Tashkent-Uzbekistan

email: dinara.saitkhanova@mail.ru

Abstract. The paper describes one of the ways of developing intermediate level reading skills through a variety of pre-reading, while-reading, and post-reading tasks. Reading in a target language is a complex interactive process that encompasses two important acquisition areas - understanding information and enhancing language proficiency. The complex nature of the process necessitates special approaches to task development. Task-based approach focuses on communicative and cognitive processes. The students are able to develop their language skills naturally by communicate with others about the task that they carry out.

Keywords: Teaching reading, task-based approach, reading comprehension, task development, interactional patterns, pre- task, content-based approach, cognitive process, capabilities.

I. Introduction

One of the receptive skills in learning English language, which should be focused on, is the reading comprehension since reading plays an important role in language learning and acquisition. Reading comprehension is also considered as the real core for reading process. It assumes that comprehension is the peak of the reading skills and the bases for all reading processes. Therefore, teaching students to read with a good comprehension must be teachers' highest priority. Furthermore, the main aim of teaching reading in junior high schools is to enable students to comprehend various reading texts. Realizing the high importance of reading comprehension ability, it is very important to find and use appropriate instructional methods, materials, activities, media, and other requirements that will help the learners improve their reading comprehension ability. In the view of this, Task-based Language Teaching (TBLT) seems to match the appropriate method to be used. TBLT is one of the teaching learning methods that its focus is put on the learners. Through TBLT, learners have the opportunity to work more autonomously and build their vocabulary and grammar. TBLT provides learners the opportunity in depth investigations of worthy knowledge. Therefore, my collaborator and I chose Task-based Language Teaching to facilitate the students with reading skills. Through this method, the students were offered opportunities to learn and use language by doing some tasks.

II. Literature review

Moreillon defines reading as using printed information and visual information to get meaning or the message conveyed in a text. In addition, Burt et al. state that reading is essentially the process of getting information from the written language. Moreover, Smith defines reading as making sense of something and then interpreting it. Moreover, Silberstein states that reading is a complex information processing skill in which the reader interacts with text in order to (re) create meaningful discourse. It has been concluded that reading is a process of thinking toward the written text to create meaning or to get the meaning conveyed. In brief, it can be stated that reading involves a complex process. [1] It requires the analysis, coordination, and interpretation of a variety of sources of information. Readers should be able to relate a text their experiences in the real world, to understand the words in the text by relating it with the knowledge possessed by the readers and to link the new information in the text with their background

knowledge. In the process of reading, comprehending the content of the written texts is the priority. In other words, comprehension is the essence of reading [2]. Raising students' awareness of main ideas in a text and exploring the organization of a text are essential for good comprehension, then. In short, reading comprehension is the ability to construct meaning from a given written text. Nunan outlines five characteristics of a task-based approach to language learning. They are: 1) an emphasis on learning to communicate through interaction in the target language, 2) the introduction of authentic texts (teaching materials) into the learning situation, 3) the provision of opportunities for learners to focus not only on language, but also on the learning process itself, 4) an enhancement of the learner's own personal experience as important contributing elements to classroom learning, and 5) an attempt to link classroom language learning with language activities outside the classroom. [3] Similar with Nunan, Willis says that task is an activity that necessarily involves language. Furthermore, Willis defines the term task as those activities where the target language is used by the learner for a communicative purpose in order to achieve an outcome.[4]

In addition, according to Richards and Rodgers, the teacher roles are related to the following issues in the communicative classroom. The first is the types of function of teachers are expected to fulfill, the second is the degree of control the teacher has over the learning takes place, the third is the degree to which the teacher is responsible for content, and the fourth is the interactional patterns that develop between the teacher and the learners. As to me, the teacher should first be the facilitator of the reading material and the designer of the task. Second, the teacher should be the observer and guide. Learners may be confused about what they should do and how they can read during the task, so the teacher should monitor the reading process of learners so as to give the timely guidance, and observe carefully at the performance of learners so as to praise them or give them the suggestion of improvement. Finally, the teacher should be a listener and learner. Learners are usually creative, so the teacher should listen to their opinions, exchange his/her idea with them and maybe he/she could learn from them, which is called that teaching benefits teachers as well as learners. In short, in a task-based language teaching class, learners play central role. [5]

III.Results and discussion:

Reading tasks have specific goals, detailed procedures and methods for students to follow. It can be said that task-based language teaching is both student-centered and task-based. In the class where students are provided with plenty of chance to be engaged in activities, the teacher is more like a patient listener rather than a talkative speaker. The goals of such reading activities are for students to explore and experience language and develop reading skills. In task-based language teaching class, the teacher designs tasks from different angles and different forms, which evoke students' interest, and organizes lessons in such a way that students can carry out the reading tasks with quality and efficiency. Furthermore, reading, in my point of view, is not a boring work. It is an active process, during which the reader tries to understand the meaning of a given text. With the guidance of the teacher, learners can understand the meaning more effectively and actively.Task-based instruction is given by the teacher to students who is in favor of learner involvement. This task is sharing by both the students and the teacher. Teacher encourage students by asking them some questions. They attend the courses actively. Students complete the given task which provides a peer-learning. Teacher teach students how to implement a task by working in a group in the class. This is called pre-task stage. Pre-task stage helps the students to do the next task correctly. It prepares them for the next task which they will work individually or in a group. After they completed a task, they are expected to manage the rest of the task with their groups. Students share their discussion and ideas about the task. A gap activity also emerges. They also evaluate their task by themselves that make them feeling confidence, and provide a peer-evaluation. The activity which the students complete the rest of the task after learning the ways. It is called ongoing -task. After the while task, the students are expected to do a new task working in groups. The subject of the task will be different from the completed one. Students will practice with their acquaintances on the new task. They share their share their ideas. At the end, they will produce

something on their own. This is called post-task. The students attempt to complete post-task, they interact and do an opinion-gap activity between students. The task based activity develops students' language skills. They improve their target language. Task-based approach and content-based approach have the aim to increase students' English acquisition. The both of two approaches enable an instrument to increase students' capabilities in English. These approaches will develop and promote students' language skills and critical thinking in English learning. The function of both approaches in language teaching that is to make real communication in the classroom between students and teachers or between students in group activity. Task-based approach and content-based approach have a role that is to teach students their needs in language. All the students desire to develop their capabilities in learning English as a Second Language (ESL) or English as a Foreign Language (EFL). The target is being centered in teaching learning process. The teachers are giving the materials and tasks to the students. Furthermore, the students learn the material and carry out the tasks in teaching learning process based on their own capabilities. They can develop the tasks with their own skills and teachers only assess the outcome what they have carried out.

Task-based approach focuses on communicative and cognitive processes. The students are able to develop their language skills naturally by communicate with others about the task that they carry out. On the other side, content-based approach concerns with information that focus on the fact of content and understanding of information. Students achieve their target based on the academic subject in order to develop their language skills. It is clear that both of these two approaches have the same goal in language teaching. These approaches improve students' capability and acquiring English language. Teachers should choose which appropriate approach for students that based on their needs and students are being able to communicate accuracy and fluency. The teacher should be following suitable steps for EFL learners at advanced level:

1. Specifying clearly the objectives for the lesson; 2. Dividing students into small four groups for each learning team. Each team should be heterogeneous of ability and gender; 3. Introducing a new reading text. Students work freely in their groups to offer different answers to the problems, brain storming, and sharing ideas, so they realize that their goal is understanding. They are continuing to work until each group member feels he/she gets the concepts involved in the exercise, through questioning each other in pairs; 4. Evaluating the students' achievement and check for understanding, by testing, using task work for the individuals separately and for the team. Rewards are given on a team basis, based on team achievement; 5. Giving the team highest score, or the team's work is displayed on the bulletin board

IV. Conclusion.

In conclusion, the study provides noteworthy findings enhancing our understanding of the benefits associated with TBI. The findings underscore the potential of TBI in improving reading comprehension, enhancing motivation for L2 reading, reducing anxiety levels, and promoting the development of L2 grit. Language educators can use these findings to inform their instructional practices and design more effective and engaging language learning experiences. By integrating task-based activities and creating supportive learning environments, educators can foster positive learning outcomes and contribute to the overall success and satisfaction of language learners. It has been concluded that reading is a process of thinking toward the written text to create meaning or to get the meaning conveyed. In brief, it can be stated that reading involves a complex process. It requires the analysis, coordination, and interpretation of a variety of sources of information. Readers should be able to relate a text their experiences in the real world, to understand the words in the text by relating it with the knowledge possessed by the readers and to link the new information in the text with their background knowledge. In the process of reading, comprehending the content of the written texts is the priority. In other words, comprehension is the essence of reading., raising students' awareness of main ideas in a text and exploring the organization of a text are essential for good comprehension, then. In short, reading comprehension is the ability to construct meaning from a given written text.

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